

BASAJAUN

Sustainable Wood Construction for Rural Development and Urban Transformation

Policy recommendations & Research needs

Uwe Kies, Vanesa Baño (InnovaWood) & Javier Garcia Jaca (Tecnalia) ◦

6 May 2024 | bit.ly/w4b-bpr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862942

basajaun-horizon.eu

Policy recommendations & Research needs

5 main recommendations for the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2025 and the preparations of FP10:

- **WP1 Forests as carbon sink and raw material supplier**
- **WP2 End of Life, Reuse, Recyclability, environmental issues**
- **WP3 Digital transformation of the forest-to-building chain**
- **WP4+5+6 Innovative materials, products, building systems**
- **WP7 Open innovation, co-creation, policy advocacy**

Recommendation #1

WP1 Forests as carbon sink and raw material supplier

- Political and scientific debate on whether there are sufficient feedstocks available to grow biobased value chains under sustainable conditions: Is there a sufficient supply? Are the climate benefits significant?
- WP1 results highlight the role of novel *digital tools* ([D1.1](#): forest inventory, wood quality, traceability), *regional markets for wood construction* ([D1.2](#): case Finland), main barriers, regional value chains and innovation ecosystems ([D1.3](#): questionnaire survey, [D1.4](#): five EU regions, [Leszczyszyn et al. 2023](#)).
- 1.1 Need for regional forest-based sector studies and market outlooks, addressing forest ecosystems + climate change and resilience + socio-economic context and impacts in the bioeconomy (Green Deal).
- 1.2 Need for a holistic systems study to make sense of the very complex situation around bio-feedstocks, the built environment and how policies set at EU level affect supply chains and wood availability.
 - Key research questions: 1. baseline: how much carbon is already stored in the built environment, 2. market scenarios for shifting biomass flows if certain uses are maximised, 3. size of the resulting carbon pools and climate impacts, 4. role of regulatory and market schemes (carbon removal credits, biodiversity targets, nature restoration, EPDs, etc.), alternative future technologies (green cement, CCS, BECCS, etc.) and side effects (biodiversity, etc.).
- 1.3 Need for substantial financial support of the Horizon 'European Partnership on Forests and Forestry' especially for R&I in innovative wood-based products and value chains ([EC DG R&I 2023](#), [EUFORE](#))

Recommendation #2

WP2 End of Life, Reuse, Recyclability, environmental issues

- WP2 reports address *zero waste* and *cascade* concepts ([D2.1](#), [D2.2](#), [Wagner & Ott 2022](#)) to improve reuse and recyclability of wood products, and *guidance for LCA* of environmental issues ([D2.3](#)).
- 2.1 Need for more R&I on circularity of wood products and value chains for carbon positive, long-life biobased materials and products that foster **repair, reuse and recycling** and address waste and environmental issues. These are priorities to move the market towards circularity and affordability.
 - Key concepts: Circularity by design, design for disassembly, long-life products, EPDs, buildings as carbon storing material banks, cascading use of biomaterials, salvage of waste wood and demolition material from urban mines, reversible joints and adhesives, integrated social LCA.
 - Policy measures: green public procurement (GPP), fiscal incentives, end-of-waste criteria, extended product responsibility (EPR), material passports, regulatory frameworks (CPR, etc.), harmonised EN standards.
- 2.2 Need for new standards for wood reuse and recycling and update of existing standards, and especially end-of-waste (EoW) criteria for promoting cascading use of wood, to facilitate the development of secondary raw materials markets for recovered wooden construction products and wood waste.
- 2.3 Rethink technology and material neutrality in the context of the climate crisis: Biobased and social innovations are only at the beginning of their technological revolution and **need a level playing field** to compete with fossil sectors => **reorient public support programmes** towards long-term transformation goals, need for major funding to accelerate R&I activities and achieve breakthroughs and market scale.

Recommendation #3

WP3 Digital transformation of the forest-to-building value chain

- Digitalisation (Industry 4.0 / 5.0) is needed at all levels, from forests, products, buildings to neighbourhoods, entire cities and landscapes. A systems view needs to be deployed to ensure competitive growth, optimisation and sustainability monitoring.
- WP3 demonstrates the *Forest 2 Building Digital Framework* (F2BDF) and validated applications (D3.1 – D3.6: architecture, backbone, DSS, [WoodLaunch](#) app, demo building monitoring | [Ott et al. 2023](#)).
- 3.1 Integration of the whole value chain and more intelligent digital design tools for biobased products and systems must be established and widely adopted. **Smart, networked solutions** will be key to enable upscaling of biobased value chains and renovation solutions. **Data gaps** in the complex value chain need to be closed to address a more integrated view for comprehensive analysis, monitoring and coordination.
 - Key themes: digital twins, digital/parametric design, AI, BIM, material traceability, 3D scanning systems, resource use modelling & optimisation, digital product passports, prefabrication, automation, robotics, biobased sensors for building products, smart facades / building envelopes, smart buildings.
- 3.2 Digital R&I specific to biobased materials need to be more fully integrated into the Horizon work programmes and other instruments. A key priority here is also digital skills development & education.

Recommendation #4

WP4+5+6 Innovative materials, products, building systems

- BASAJAUN has developed and scaled up a range of innovative biobased materials and products (D4.1-D4.10), components (D5.1-D5.8) to implement them in a full-scale demonstration building (D6.1-D6.6).
- 4.1 Improved building systems for long-life biobased materials and products need to drive the market towards more circular, carbon positive, affordable solutions. **Industrialisation of wood construction** using more off-site production, prefabrication and digitalisation is the main priority, together with upskilling of factory workers. More R&I pilots of **circular, biomanufacturing solutions** with industry/SMEs are needed.
- 4.2 A European testbed network of biobased demonstrators and test buildings is needed to better exploit R&I results and to build a **shared, connected testing infrastructure**. The goal is to speed up validation, upscaling and deployment across countries, and to support higher awareness and skills/education.
 - Key themes for the wood sector: novel engineered wood products (EWP), wood-based insulation materials (including next generation of thinner materials better suited for renovation), reversible connectors, biobased adhesives, underused wood materials (alternative species/hardwoods, salvaged wood, post-consumer wood), modified wood, wood + other biobased materials.
 - Key themes for the construction sector: prefabrication, hybrid, modular construction systems, maximising resource efficiency, lightweight materials, insulation properties, circular design, circular business models, smart renovation packages, energy efficiency, embodied carbon, climate adaptation.
- These needs are well aligned with [New European Bauhaus \(NEB\)](#), [Circular Bio-based Europe](#) and [Built4People](#).

Recommendation #4 (cont.)

WP4+5+6 Innovative materials, products, building systems

- **4.3 Harmonised standards and building regulations:** Building design according to Eurocodes requires available harmonised *EN standards* and *European Assessment Documents* (EAD) provided by CEN and EOTA, respectively, that allow to comply with the performance and sustainable requirements under the [Construction Products Regulation \(CPR\)](#).
- **Wood grading:** Update EN standards under CEN TC 124 WG2: Solid Timber with the properties of alternative wood species (undervalued, hardwoods, etc.) and review origins if needed (climate change may affect the properties of already graded wood species). Develop specific standards with the detailed wood properties for numerical simulation of complex structures using finite element modelling (FEM), not covered yet by any EN standard.
- **Innovative EWP and building systems:** Harmonised EN standards under CEN TC 124 WG3: Glued laminated timber, WG4: Connections, WG 5: prefabricated walls, roofs and floors defining the manufacturing requirements and properties of innovative EWP and building systems are key for safety design, efficient use of resources, and design for disassembly. Specific EN standards for EWP manufactured using alternative/underused wood species are required.
- **Recovered/reclaimed wood:** Wood grading of recovered wood and EWP manufactured from recovered wood are not yet covered by any EN standard under CEN TC 124: Timber Structures and CEN TC 112: Wood-based panels. An approved sorting and grading system for recovered wood is key for the development of wood-based panels and EWP, respectively.
- **Sustainability for timber products:** Up-to-date EN standards under CEN TC 350: Sustainability of Construction Works. Specific *Product Categories Rules* (PCR) for timber products are needed for [Environmental Product Declarations \(EPD\)](#).

Recommendation #5

Innovate
With
Wood

WP7 Open innovation, co-creation, policy advocacy

- WP7 explored regional innovation roadmaps (D7.1, [Kies et al. 2022](#)) and established the pilot of the *Open Innovation Platform 'Innovate With Wood'* (OIP, D7.2 – D7.4) for biobased, circular and digital innovations in the construction sector.
- The *New European Bauhaus Facility* can become a main instrument for the transformation of the built environment. It can drive participatory people-centred projects, leverage **synergies** of funding instruments (EU, regional, national), engage **GPP** stakeholders and approaches, lead **social innovation** and **inclusion** (governance, diversity, democracy), and include green/social impact investment, donors, etc.
- 5.1 A holistic socio-technological innovation roadmap of the biobased construction sector needs to be co-designed with stakeholders in the construction ecosystem (forestry, construction, engineering, architecture, urban planners, financial sector, etc). A measurable target for scaling up the biobased sector and tools for implementation (regulatory, policy, financial, insurance) should be developed. The roadmap can **mobilise policy & financial audiences** to unlock support and investment for the wider adoption of innovative, regenerative biobased solutions, circularity, sustainable buildings, and social value.
- 5.2 The NEB approach is suited to **encourage innovative businesses and citizens** to orchestrate meaningful **co-creation** for climate positive products and solutions. Useful tools to accelerate the transition with 'wood + biobased' include: regulatory sandboxes, GPP, communities of practice (CoP), living labs, action research, codesign competitions, open calls, citizen science, prizes, science communicators.

Further reading: wood4bauhaus.eu/news/neb-open-letter-2023

BASAJAUN

References

References – Public reports

- **D1.1: European forest as raw material supplier in the construction sector.** Lanvin, J.-D., Blanquet, I., Kouyoumji, J.-L., Leszczyszyn, E., Augustyniak, D., Heräjärvi, H., Verkasalo, E., Calvillo, A., Araya-Letelier, G., García Jaca, J., den Bakker, I., & Maltoni, C. (2021). BASAJAUN Public report D1.1. FCBA, LRN-ITD, LUKE. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781145
- **D1.2: Building with wood as a driver for sustainable development in rural regions.** Heräjärvi, H., Lehtonen, O., Hiltunen, A.-P., Muilu, T., Verkasalo, E., Lanvin, J.-D., Leszczyszyn, E., & Bidzińska, G. (2021). BASAJAUN Public report D1.2. LUKE, FCBA, LRN-ITD. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781092
- **D1.3: Guidelines to foster building with wood.** Leszczyszyn, E., Augustyniak, D., Bidzińska, Gabriela, Noskowiak, A., Heräjärvi, H., Verkasalo, E., Lanvin, J.-D., Blanquet, I., Kouyoumji, J.-L., Wahlström, M., & García Jaca, J. (2021). BASAJAUN Public report D1.3. ITD, LUKE, FCBA, VTT, TEC. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781143
- **D1.4: Holistic approach to the building with wood value chain.** Lanvin, J.-D., Romih, P., Ba, H., Kouyoumji, J.-L., Leszczyszyn, E., Augustyniak, D., & Heräjärvi, H. (2021). BASAJAUN Public report D1.4. FCBA, LRN-ITD, LUKE. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781275
- **D2.1: Recommendations of zero-waste in wood-based products.** Vares, S., Wahlström, M., Hradil, P., Vainio, T., Jetsu, P., Henderson, R., Nikkilä, M., Arrizabalaga, U., & Schirp, A. (2021). BASAJAUN Public report D2.1. VTT, Etcetera, Elastopoli, Garnica, WKI. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781283
- **D2.3: Methodological recommendations and guidelines for LCA assessment.** Vares, S., Gourdet, C., Kouyoumji, J.-L., Wagner, A., Ott, S., & Barriuso, M. (2021). BASAJAUN Public report D2.3. VTT, FCBA, TUM, Tecnalia. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4781295

References – Papers, presentations

- Baño, V., Kies, U., & Zaton, P. (2023). **Research needs for European species in a scenario of increasing structural wood demand for building**. 32nd International Conference on Wood Science and Technology (ICWST), Zagreb, Croatia. InnovaWood. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10373144
- Baño, V., Kies, U., García Jaca, J., Astudillo, J., & Minderhoud, T. (2023). **Demonstrating innovative wood-based materials and products in green public procurement: the co-design of the BASAJAUN demo building following the New European Bauhaus values and principles**. InnoRenew CoE International Conference 2023 (IRIC 2023), Izola, Slovenia. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8344027
- Kies, U. (2023). **Wood4Bauhaus: Europe's green transformation in policy, industry and society discovers wood science and innovation**. Keynote presentation. World Conference on Timber Engineering (WCTE), Oslo, Norway. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8092336
- Kies, U. (2022). **Climate neutral building with wood: Strategies and Research Needs for the forest-based sector in the Green Transformation**. Woodrise Webinar Series. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7117525
- Kies, U., Kouyoumji, J.-L., Romih, P., Heräjärvi, H., Weckroth, M., Muilu, T., Leszczyszyn, E., Augustyniak-Wysocka, D., Bidzińska, G., Saez de Zerain Albizu, A., & García Jaca, J. (2022). **Transformation needs of wood construction sectors in five European regions**. Luke - Natural Resources Institute Finland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7121329
- Leszczyszyn, E., Heräjärvi, H., Verkasalo, E., et al. (2022). **The Future of Wood Construction: Opportunities and Barriers Based on Surveys in Europe and Chile**. Sustainability 2022, 14(7), 4358. doi.org/10.3390/su14074358
- Ott, S., Rudena, A., Kies, U., Wagner, A., & Jancke, O. (2023). **Digital twin framework for visual exploration of material flows and carbon impacts of engineered wood supply chains from forest to buildings**. World Conference on Timber Engineering (WCTE), Oslo, Norway. doi.org/10.52202/069179-0586
- Wagner, A. & Ott, S. (2022). **Cascading Wood-based Construction Products – A Guideline for Product Development**. E3S Web Conference Vol. 349, LCM 2021. doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202234904009

Policy recommendations to the NEB

Joint documents and contributions by the W4B Alliance

- *Virtual Conference* "The New European Bauhaus: How can the wood sector engage, contribute and co-create?" (8 April 2021) | w4b/conference-2021
- *Research Needs & Priorities* supporting Sustainable Construction with Nature-based Materials under the European Green Deal (23 June 2021) | bit.ly/w4brn
- *Policy recommendations* to encourage nature-based materials like wood in construction and renovation of the built environment (23 June 2021) | bit.ly/w4bpr
- *Horizon NEB NEXUS Report* by Schellnhuber et al. for EC DG R&I & JRC. Contributions from the W4B Alliance to various challenges (Feb 2022) | HE-NEB Nexus
- *Open Support Letter for the NEB*: The EU forest-based sector's role in the transformation of the built and living environment (addressed to the Permanent Representations of the EU countries to the EU, 7 Dec 2023) | bit.ly/w4bneb2023

Contributors

BASAJAUN consortium

- **TECNALIA:** Astudillo, Julen; Barriuso Astigarraga, Mikel; Armijo, Alberto; Puente, Sheila
- **LUKE:** Heräjärvi, Henrik; Weckroth, Mikko; Verkasalo, Erkki; Muilu, Toivo
- **FCBA:** Lanvin, Jean-Denis; Kouyoumji, Jean-Luc; Gourdet, Claire; Ba, Haroun; Romih, Peter
- **PIT:** Leszczyszyn, Ewa; Augustyniak-Wysocka, Dobrochna; Bidzińska, Gabriela
- **TUM:** Kirschstein (née Wagner), Anna; Ott, Stephan
- **VTT:** Vares, Sirje; Wahlström, Margareta; Oksanen, Antti
- **RISE:** Bomark, Peter; Lycken, Anders; Brunklaus, Birgit; Funk, Peter
- **UNStudio:** Minderhoud, Tom
- **Paramountric:** Rudenå, Andreas
- **BaskEgur:** Zabala, Irati; Saez, Aitor

Wood4Bauhaus Alliance

- **CEI-Bois & EOS:** Brannen, Paul; Melegari, Silvia
- **EPF:** Pinnington, Clive; Wijnendaele, Kris; Kuhl, Alexis
- **EFBWW:** Gehring, Rolf; Uzelac, Slavica
- **InnoRenew CoE:** Kutnar, Andreja; Burnard, Michael
- **InnovaWood:** Jancke, Oliver

BASAJAUN

Project summary

Building A SustainAble Joint between rurAl and UrbaN Areas Through Circular And Innovative Wood Construction Value Chains

Horizon 2020 IA grant no. 862942 | Call LC-RUR-11 | Oct 2019 – April 2024

Consortium - 29 partners, 12 countries | Total budget 12.2 M€ | Total EC grant 10M€

Coordinator - Tecnalia Research & Innovation, Azpeitia, Spain

Forest-to-building supply chain

Innovations in wood-based products

WP1 Sustainable wood construction value chain

European forest potential, rural and urban areas

WP2 Recyclability, environmental issues

End of Life - recyclability and reusability of BASAJAUN products

WP3 Forest 2 building digital framework

Design of a 'backbone' architecture

WP4 Innovative materials

Fire retarded WPC ◦ Foamed WPC ◦ Insulations ◦ Structural insulation panels (SIP) ◦ Coatings

WP5 Building systems and products

Structural components, Facades, Roofs, Bio-composite profiles

WP6 Demo building

Residential school building in Southern France

Southern demo building, New Aquitaine, France

BASAJAUN

Horizon 2020 no. 862942
basajaun-horizon.eu

Pictures / design © UNStudio

The team made it happen !

BASAJAUN

Uwe Kies

uwe.kies@innovawood.eu

Vanesa Baño

vanesa.bano@innovawood.eu

tecnal:a

MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH
& TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

Javier García Jaca

javier.garciajaca@tecnalia.com

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862942

bit.ly/w4b-bpr

tecnalia/basajaun

basajaun-horizon.eu

#basajaunhorizon